

Electronic Information Sources And Their Role In Meeting The Needs Of The Beneficiaries In The Libraries Of The Colleges Of Diyala University

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Abstract

The research aims to identify the electronic information sources available in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University and the extent to which the electronic information sources meet the needs of the beneficiaries and to identify the obstacles and problems that prevent the provision of these sources. The research used the survey method and relied on the interview and questionnaire as tools for data collection. The research reached a number of results. Including a lack of staffing in the libraries during the research and a lack of electronic information sources and the percentage of paper sources is the highest and most of the beneficiaries turn towards paper sources of information because they are more available than electronic. A number of recommendations have been made, including the need to strengthen libraries with electronic information sources and that these sources are diverse and characterized by modernity. The information it contains, the necessity of providing ways and means to announce the sources of information provided by the library, and the necessity of creating a special directory for the library, provided that it includes informing the beneficiaries about all the electronic information sources that reach the library of their field of interest.

Introduction

The era in which we live today is the information age, in which interest in information has begun to increase due to its importance and role in meeting the needs of the beneficiaries, as well as interest in information sources in its various traditional and electronic forms, as electronic information sources are an important source of information and a suitable alternative to traditional sources in the era of information explosion, with which it is difficult to control. Because of this amount of information, most libraries, especially university ones, have sought to acquire it to benefit from it, and since these libraries provide their services to their beneficiaries, which in turn leads to the development of their services, so university libraries must provide modern electronic information sources to meet the needs of their beneficiaries, and based on the foregoing. This research came to identify electronic information sources, their types and importance, and the extent to which electronic information sources meet the needs of the beneficiaries of the libraries of Diyala University faculties, and to identify the strengths and weaknesses in providing them.

General framework for research

Searchproblem

Electronic sources of information imposed themselves on libraries on the grounds that they are a more important source and source of information, especially electronic ones, and these sources have become an important part of university libraries because they are an essential focus of scientific research. The importance of electronic information sources and their role in meeting the needs of the beneficiaries in the libraries of the colleges of the University of Diyala came this study, where T represents the problem of research in the following questions:

- What are the forms of electronic information resources provided by the college's libraries of Diyala University?
- To what extent do electronic information sources meet the needs of the beneficiaries in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University?
- What are the obstacles or problems that prevent the provision of electronic information sources?

The importance of research

The importance of the research comes from the importance that electronic information sources attach to the beneficiaries of libraries and information centers, especially with the great and increasing diversity of information in various fields, as electronic information sources came to facilitate and speed up access to information by their beneficiaries in various ways, whether through the websites of libraries on the Internet or from Through laser discs or other means that enable the beneficiaries to benefit correctly, and through this the importance of searching for electronic information sources and meeting the needs of the beneficiaries. The emergence of the colleges libraries of Diyala University.

Research objectives

The research seeks to achieve the following objectives:

- Identify the forms of electronic information sources available in the college's libraries of Diyala University.
- The extent to which electronic information sources meet the needs of beneficiaries in the libraries of Diyala University faculties.
- Identifying obstacles and problems that prevent the provision of these resources.

Theoretical framework for research

Electronic information sources

Electronic information resources are defined as those sources that deal with and digitize electronic materials, which can be accessed from the internal library database or from the World Wide Web. Materials include e-books, e-magazines, e-newspapers, etc. (Urhiewhu&Omah, 2016, p. 2)

Reasons or factors for the emergence of electronic information sources

There are many reasons or factors which gave rise to the sources of information which can be divided as follows (Ghalib, 2011, pages 39-40)

1. Informational factors related to the features of intellectual production: such as the multiplicity of languages in which intellectual production is published, its size, the diversity of the number of its sources, and the overlapping of its topics.
2. Retroactive factors: which relate to the needs of the beneficiaries, such as: the speed of obtaining information in the least time and least effort?
3. Technical and technological factors: They are represented in information and communication technology and have a major role in the emergence of electronic information sources such as: the Internet, computer technologies, and communication technologies and data transmission.
4. Economic factors: These factors include the high cost of obtaining traditional printed information sources, such as the high prices of paper and ink, the cost of producing, printing and distributing traditional sources, labor, technical procedures and others.

Advantages of electronic information sources

Electronic information sources have many advantages that can be summarized in the following (Essam, 2011, p. 218)

1. The possibility of communicating with the beneficiary from wherever he is and obtaining information due to the possibility of the availability of electronic sources of information for him, such as knowing weather conditions, finding job opportunities, seeing the latest news and others.
2. Ease of use of computers and communication technologies. The beneficiary has access to the information available in electronic databases in remote or scattered locations outside the library.
3. Electronic information sources provide a spatial space, because printed sources constitute a problem for libraries and information centers because they occupy a large space. (Jamal, 2015, p. 55)
4. Access to information that may be restricted to the user due to geographical or financial location.
5. Access to more available information and provide additional expanded links to related content. (Adniran, 2013, p. 319)

Disadvantages of electronic information sources

The disadvantages of electronic information sources are summarized as follows:

1. Many libraries and information centers that are concerned with acquiring electronic resources lack infrastructure and technology in the field of communications, hardware and software to provide electronic resources(.Amer, Ribhi, and Iman, 2009, pg. 494)
2. The electronic form of the sources constitutes a psychological factor for some readers. Some people see that they prefer paper sources while they are relaxing at home, plane or train) .Wisal, 2015, p. 816)
3. Dealing with electronic information sources suffers from the problem of continuous change in the technology of hardware and software used to deal with these sources(.Jamal, 2015, p. 58)
4. The segment of its users has shrunk due to poor training and control over its use, and it is in constant need of maintenance.
5. Its excessive use leads to health problems for its users(Fourth, 2015, pp. 49-50)

Forms of electronic information sources

Electronic information sources have many forms, which are summarized as follows:

1. Electronic books: Electronic books are books that are provided in a digital format for exit or use via an Internet browser, computer or any other electronic device such as an electronic book reader. (Prisoner, 2017, p. 62)
2. Electronic periodicals: These are publications issued periodically and distributed on CDs or available on the Internet and distributed via e-mail or otherwise. E-journals may be print or electronic only. (Mohammed Amani, 2007, p. 52)

3. Electronic University Theses and Theses: This form of electronic resources has recently begun to spread over the Internet as full texts, after we became accustomed to using the services of global bibliographic databases.
4. Automated indexes for all types of libraries: Most libraries tended to provide automated indexing services for their collections in a sophisticated way, and the traditional indexing services and the problems they suffer from were discontinued, and turned to standardized automated indexes and then indexes. Available to everyone online. Public Access Catalogs (OPAC)
5. Global bibliographic databases or complete online databases: They are among the widely used electronic resources in libraries, especially university and specialized libraries, because they provide their services in an expanded manner by making them available to hundreds of thousands of research papers, articles, conference proceedings and others without obtaining access to them in the library.
6. Internal databases: The library designs and builds these databases according to its needs, which can be made available online via networks such as the Internet to provide its services.
7. Electronic resources: which is called the Global Virtual Library, and it is websites for individuals, institutions, libraries, universities or other sources of information to meet the information needs of those who request it. (Rebhi and Iman, 2014, pp. 74-75)
8. Electronic information sources stored on CDs: They are modern media for storing information, as they carry large amounts of data in different forms, whether text, audio or visual. (Ghalib, 2011, p. 531)
9. Electronic publishing: It means the production and provision of information through computers or long-range means of communication from the author or publisher to the final beneficiary directly through communication networks. (Raafat, 2006, p. 11)
10. Electronic references: Reference services are available through the Internet, which is provided through e-mail or instant chat. It is a set of approved questions available on the website. These questions are answered by the Library's reference section. (Amal 2007, p. 56).

Practical framework for research

First :Diyala University faculties' libraries

History of Diyala University

Diyala University was established in 1999 and is considered one of the medium-sized universities, with a capacity of 12 thousand students after the completion of the establishment of all its service facilities. It is a specialized scientific and cultural center within the governorate. It was previously established through the establishment of the College of Education, Engineering and Basic Education (formerly Teachers College), which was previously affiliated with Al-Mustansiriya University. Establishing other colleges and looking to achieve distinction between their local and Arab counterparts. Universities to be pioneers and distinguished in the field of higher education and scientific research (1)

Establishing the Libraries of Diyala University Colleges

Table No. (1) Shows the years of establishment of Diyala University faculties' libraries. It turns out that the Library of the College of Basic Education and the Library of the College of Education for Human Sciences are among the oldest libraries if they were established in 1994, followed by the Library of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences, which was established in 1996. Because the colleges to which these libraries belong were affiliated to the formations of Al-Mustansiriya University earlier, and the two most recent libraries they are the two libraries of the College of Fine Arts and the Library of Al-Mustansiriya University. Miqdad College of Education, which was established in 2012.

Table (1) the years in which the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University were established

Foundation	Library name	No
1994	College of Basic Education library	1
1994	Library of the College of Education for the Humanities	2
1996	Library of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences	3
1998	College of Engineering Library	4
2001	Science College Library	5

2002	Library of the Faculty of Law and Political Science	6
2002	Medical College Library	7
2002	College of Veterinary Medicine Library	8
2004	College of Agriculture Library	9
2008	Library of the College of Education for Pure Sciences	10
2009	Library of the College of Administration and Economics	11
2009	Library of the College of Islamic Sciences	12
2012	College of Fine Arts Library	13
2012	Al-Miqdad College of Education Library	14

Staffing in the colleges libraries of Diyala University

Table (2) shows the scientific specialization of workers in the faculties of the Libraries of Diyala University, who are specialists in the field of information and libraries, and non-specialists from other disciplines. The total number of library employees during the study was (46) employees, as shown in the following detail: The total number of library employees. The College of Basic Education includes (5) employees, including an employee specialized in information and libraries, with (20) of the total employees, and (4) employees from other disciplines at (80%). As for the library of the College of Education for Human Sciences, the total number of its employees is (8), all of whom are from other disciplines at a rate of (100%), and the library of the College of Physical Education. 4 employees working in the field of sports sciences and all of them from other disciplines (100%). As for the library of the College of Engineering, the total number of employees reached (3), all of them from other disciplines (100%). As for the library of the College of Science, the total number of employees reached (2), all of them from other disciplines, at a rate of (100%). As for the library of the Faculty of Law, the number of employees in it is (2) employees from other specialties (100%), while the library of the Faculty of Medicine has the total number of employees in it. They are (4) employees, all of them from other specialties (100%). As for the library of the College of Veterinary Medicine, the number of employees is (4) employees, including an employee specialized in information and libraries (25%) and (3) employees from other specialties (75%). As for the library of the College of Agriculture, the total number of employees in it is (2) employees from other disciplines, at a rate of (100%). As for the library of the College of Education for Pure Sciences, the total number of employees is (3), including an employee specialized in information and libraries (33%) and (2). Employees from other disciplines (66%), and the library of the College of Management and Economics includes (2) employees from other disciplines (100%), as well as the library of the college. The number of employees in it was (2) employees from other disciplines (100%), while the total number of employees in the library of the College of Fine Arts was (3) employees, including one (1) employee. It specialized in information and libraries with a percentage of (33%) and (2) employees from other disciplines (66%), then the library of the Faculty of Education Miqdad, which contains a number of employees. Two (2) employees, including one employee specialized in information and libraries (50%) and one employee from other specialties (50%).

On the other hand, Table No. (2) shows the number of specialists in the field of information and libraries, as the total number of employees specialized in information and libraries in libraries during the study was (5) employees of the total, constituting (11%) and the number of employees from other disciplines (41) employees with a percentage (89%), and it is noted that there are a small number of workers in the field of information and libraries, and that most libraries during the study period do not have a staff of specialists, and this negatively affects the level and performance in terms of organization, arranging the library group, providing services and upgrading the level of libraries.

Table No. (2) Shows the scientific specialization of library workers during the study

Total	percentage	Other specialties	percentage	Specializing in information and libraries	Library name	No
5	%80	4	%20	1	College of Basic Education library	1
8	%100	8	-	-	College of Education for the Humanities Library	2
4	%100	4	-	-	Library of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences	3
3	%100	3	-	-	College of Engineering Library	4
2	%100	2	-	-	College of Science Library	5
2	%100	2	-	-	Law College Library	6
4	%100	4	-	-	Medical College Library	7
4	%75	3	%25	1	College of Veterinary Medicine Library	8
2	%100	2	-	-	College of Agriculture Library	9
3	%66	2	%33	1	Library of the College of Education for Pure Sciences	10
2	100	2	-	-	Library of the College of Administration and Economics	11
2	100	2	-	-	Library of the College of Islamic Sciences	12
3	%66	2	%33	1	College of Fine Arts Library	13
2	%50	1	%50	1	Al-Miqdad College of Education Library	14
46	100	41	100	5	total summation	
		%89		%11	percentage	

The library collection available in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University

Table No. (3) Shows the set of libraries available in the colleges libraries of Diyala University. The total number of paper and electronic sources reached (78064) sources of paper information sources, where books constituted the highest percentage with a total of (52576) books and (67%) of the total, followed by university theses with a total number of (52576). A total of (7370) characters with a percentage of (9%), followed by periodicals with a total of (4442) periodicals and a percentage of (5%), then various paper sources such as (brochures, pamphlets and booklets) with a total of (222) sources and a percentage of (0.28%) of the total.

As for electronic information sources, university theses constituted the highest percentage of total (7805) university electronic messages, and (10%) of the total, and that most of these university theses were donated by university professors in the form of CDs (DVD: each disk contains On a group of university theses that are downloaded to the computers in the library to benefit from, followed by laser discs with a total of (3583) discs (4%) and then e-books with a total of (2066) and (2%) of the total, and it is noted that There is a clear lack of electronic information sources in libraries throughout the study period, and they are insufficient to meet the needs of beneficiaries of electronic information sources.

Table (3) the library holdings available in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University

Total	Various paper	laser discs	periodicals	Undergraduate Theses	books	Library name	No
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		sources												
					electronic form			paper shape		electronic form	paper shape	electronic form	paper shape	
137	78	45	200	-	155	2600	2722	-	8056	College of Basic Education library			1	
220	80	50	1100	-	1614	2050	1615	-	15651	College of Education for the Humanities Library			2	
320	3	-	380	-	70	-	213	-	2540	Library of the College of Physical Education and Sports Sciences			3	
349	0	-	29	-	21	-	172	-	3268	College of Engineering Library			4	
781	6	127	-	-	687	1838	498	1567	3099	College of Science Library			5	
608	5	-	-	-	400	-	185	-	5500	Law College Library			6	
284	9	-	-	-	510	-	116	-	2223	Medical College Library			7	
217	0	-	40	-	463	-	157	100	1410	College of Veterinary Medicine Library			8	
315	7	-	1109	-	100	-	695	-	1253	College of Agriculture Library			9	
351	8	-	610	-	75	864	759	359	851	Library of the College of Education for Pure Sciences			10	
311	8	-	-	-	96	-	27	-	2995	Library of the College of Administration and Economics			11	
236	5	-	-	-	75	-	90	-	2200	Library of the College of Islamic Sciences			12	
299	1	-	115	-	76	25	75	-	2700	College of Fine Arts Library			13	
144	4	-	-	-	100	428	46	40	830	Al-Miqdad College of Education Library			14	
780	64	222	3583	-	4442	7805	7370	2066	52576	Total				
100		%0.28	%4	-	%5	%10	%9	%2	%67	percentage				

Second: resolution analysis

The identification of electronic information sources was applied to (429) students and postgraduate students in the scientific and humanities faculties at the University of Diyala, who watched the researcher and the moon to obtain a doctorate, and their number was (53) and the master's number (319), and among them were those who study in scientific faculties and promised (203). And some of them are studying in the faculties of humanities and their number (169). The results showed that the differences are statistically significant in favor of the hypothetical arithmetic mean (2) over the arithmetic mean of the sample, that is, the hypothetical arithmetic mean is greater than the arithmetic mean of the sample and for the axis Electronic information Sources and their inquiries, and when the value of the significance level is less than (0.05) the differences are in favor of the larger arithmetic mean, which is hypothetical, and this means that the focus of electronic information sources and their inquiries do not meet the needs of beneficiaries in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University, and Table No. (4) And (5) explain this in detail.

Table (4) shows the frequencies and their percentages for each query. The second axis: electronic information sources and their importance in the library

Resolution scale, frequencies and percentages for each query			Inquiries	No
I do not agree 1	neutral 2	Agreed 3		
295	63	14	The availability of my college library on electronic information sources prompted the creation of modern ways to make information available	1
%79.3	%16.9	%3.8		
267	89	16	Providing ways and means to advertise the electronic information resources available in the library ,contributing to your benefit from them more	2
%71.8	%23.9	%4.3		

251	92	29	Providing electronic information sources in the library is a reason to increase the demand for them	3
%67.5	%24.7	%7.8		
207	111	54	The lack of electronic information sources does not negatively affect the library	4
%55.6	%29.8	%14.5		
270	82	20	Possess knowledge in some techniques to help your search through electronic sources of information provided by the college library and take advantage of them	5
%72.6	%22.0	%5.4		
224	103	45	The information provided by the electronic resources in the library meets your needs and supports your specialization	6
%60.2	%27.7	%12.1		
187	132	53	Prefer to use electronic information sources available in your college library more than traditional sources in research and information acquisition	7
%50.3	%35.5	%14.2		
257	91	24	The use of electronic information sources helps you in the possibility of downloading, printing and transferring the information they contain	8
%69.1	%24.5	%6.5		
271	68	33	The diversity of electronic resources provided by the library has made good use of them	9
%72.8	%18.3	%8.9		
273	75	24	Using the electronic information resources provided by your college library provides you with multiple options to search for information	10
%73.4	%20.2	%6.5		

Table (5) Explains inferential statistics using the t-test in terms of the hypothetical arithmetic mean (for the community) to identify electronic information sources and their inquiries

Arrange inquiry on axis	The results of the t-test in terms of the hypothetical arithmetic mean for each query						Inquiries	No
	relative weight	Test significance level	T value	standard deviation	SMA	the number		
10	%41.50	0.000	28.531-	0.511	1.245	372	The availability of my college library on electronic information sources prompted the creation of modern ways to make information available	1
9	%44.17	0.000	23.514-	0.553	1.325	372	Providing ways and means to advertise the electronic information resources available in the library ,contributing to your benefit from them more	2
4	%46.77	0.000	18,254-	0.631	1.403	372	Providing electronic information sources in the library is a reason to increase the demand for them	3
2	%52.97	0.000	10.857-	0.731	1.589	372	The lack of electronic information sources does not negatively affect the library	4

8	%44.27	0.000	22.604-	0.573	1.328	372	Possess knowledge in some techniques to help your search through electronic sources of information provided by the college library and take advantage of them	5
3	%50.63	0.000	13.219-	0.702	1.519	372	The information provided by the electronic resources in the library meets your needs and supports your specialization	6
1	%54.67	0.000	9.664-	0.719	1.640	372	Prefer to use electronic information sources available in your college library more than traditional sources in research and information acquisition	7
5	%45.8	0.000	20.022-	0.603	1.374	372	The use of electronic information sources helps you in the possibility of downloading, printing and transferring the information they contain	8
6	%45.33	0.000	19.295-	0.640	1.360	372	The diversity of electronic resources provided by the library has made good use of them	9
7	%44.37	0.000	21.782-	0.593	1.331	372	Using the electronic information resources provided by your college library provides you with multiple options to search for information	10
-	-	0.000	31.387-	0.362	1.411	372	The results of the axis as a whole : electronic information sources and their importance in the library	

Table (5) shows deductive statistics using the test in terms of the arithmetic mean of premise (community) to identify the sources of information and electronic inquiries ,where the results showed reached that statistically significant differences in favor of the arithmetic mean premise of (2) on the arithmetic mean of the sample means that the arithmetic average The hypothesis is greater than the arithmetic average of the inquiries, which is (1.411), which means that all the inquiries do not meet the needs of the beneficiaries, and by analyzing the answers retrieved from that category that was chosen and shown in Table (5), the following becomes clear:

1. The first inquiry (the availability of my college library on electronic information sources prompted the creation of modern ways to make information available) and it ranked tenth with an arithmetic average of (1.245) and a relative weight (41.50%), which shows that there are no modern ways to make information available due to the lack of electronic information sources provided by the libraries in question ,and if they are available, they are not characterized by modernity.
2. The second query) providing ways and means to announce the electronic information sources available in the library contributed to your benefit from them more (came in the ninth rank with an average of (1.325) and a relative weight of (44.17%), which means that there is a weakness in the methods and means of advertising about sources Electronic information, which contributes to the beneficiaries' benefit from what is available in these libraries from electronic sources of information, and the reason for this is due to the weakness of technical and material capabilities and the weakness of their presence on the Internet.
3. The third query (providing electronic information sources in the library is a reason for the increase in demand for it) was ranked fourth, with an average of (1.403) and a relative weight (46.77%). This means that the increase in demand for the library is not due to the availability of electronic information sources exclusively, but rather due to the actual needs of the beneficiaries of the modern resources that serve the specialization provided by the library, whether it is traditional or electronic.
4. The fourth query (the lack of electronic information sources does not negatively affect the library), which ranked second with an arithmetic average of (1,589) and a relative weight of (52.97%), which means that the lack of electronic information sources has a negative impact on the library, especially as we live in the age of technology Information sources have a major role in meeting the needs of the beneficiaries.

5. The fifth inquiry (possession of knowledge in some technologies that helps you in searching through electronic information sources provided by your college library and benefiting from them) came in eighth place and obtained an arithmetic average (1.328) and a relative weight of (44.27%). The beneficiaries are knowledgeable in some techniques, but it is not possible to actually benefit from the sources of information provided by the library because they are few or because they are not recent.
6. The sixth inquiry (the information provided by the electronic resources in the library meets your needs and supports your specialization) ranked third with an arithmetic average of (1.519) and a relative weight of (50.63%), which means that the information provided by electronic resources in the libraries under study is few and not diverse .It does not meet the needs of the beneficiaries or support their specialization.
7. The seventh query) prefer to use electronic information sources available in your college library than traditional sources in research and information collection (came in the first place with an arithmetic average of (1,640) and a relative weight of (54.67%), which means that the beneficiaries of the research libraries prefer to use Traditional (paper) sources are more than electronic sources because they are more available than electronic and support specialization and do not need techniques to benefit from them and are inexpensive.
8. The eighth inquiry (the use of electronic information sources helps you in the possibility of downloading, printing and transferring the information they contain) is ranked fifth with an arithmetic average of (1.374) and a relative weight of (45.8%), which means the difficulty of downloading, printing and transferring the information it contains to the majority of beneficiaries of libraries around the world .Research and the reason for this is due to the lack of electronic resources and the weak technical capabilities available in these libraries.
9. The ninth inquiry (the diversity of electronic resources provided by the library achieved good use of it) ranked sixth with an arithmetic average of (1.360) and a relative weight of (45.33%), which shows that the electronic resources provided by the library are not diverse and do not achieve good and effective use by the beneficiaries of the library .Search Libraries.
10. The tenth inquiry (using electronic information sources provided by your college library provides you with multiple options to search for information) ranked seventh with an arithmetic average of (1.331) and a relative weight of (44.37%), which means that the electronic resources provided by these libraries do not provide Multiple options to search for it or for the information it provides because it is limited to one form in most libraries or two forms, and sometimes some libraries do not have any form of electronic information

Findings and Recommendations

First: the results

The research reached a set of results, including:

1. The number of employees in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University reached (46) employees, the number of employees from other disciplines (41) employees at a rate of (89%), and the number of employees specialized in the field of information and libraries is (5) employees, at a rate of (11%), a very weak percentage.
2. A group of libraries available in the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University, in paper and electronic forms, amounting to (78064) sources. As for paper sources of information, books constituted the highest percentage with a total of (52576) books, at a rate of (67%). As for electronic information sources, university theses constituted the highest percentage with a total of (7805) university electronic theses at a rate of (10%), and there is a significant shortage of electronic information sources.
3. The majority of beneficiaries turn to paper sources of information because they are more available than electronic information sources for the majority of Diyala University colleges libraries.
4. Most of the beneficiaries agreed that the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University suffer from a weakness in the ways and means of announcing the electronic information sources available in the auditors' clerks, the reason for the doubling of the presence of these libraries on the Internet and the weakness of technical and material capabilities.

Second: Recommendations

Through this research, researchers recommend the following:

1. The necessity of strengthening the libraries of the colleges of Diyala University with electronic information sources, and that these sources are diverse and characterized by the up-to-date information they contain.
2. The libraries affiliated to the colleges of Diyala University should have an electronic presence on the Internet that helps them to advertise their paper and electronic library collections.
3. The necessity of creating a special directory for the library, provided that it includes informing the beneficiaries of all the electronic information sources that reach the library of their interest.

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